

Current State Of Subalpine And Alpine Vegetation In The Territory Of Gusar

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The article discusses the current state of vegetation and species diversity of alpine and subalpine zones in Gusar district of Azerbaijan. Data concerning some edificators and dominants of meadows of the investigated areas and the basic vegetative associations are cited.

Key words: *Pasture, forest, subalpine, alpine, type of vegetation, association*